

AUTOMATED ANDROID MALWARE DETECTION USING OPTIMAL ENSEMBLE LEARNING APPROACH OF CYBERSECURITY

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ABSTRACT

Current technological advancement in computer systems has transformed the lives of humans from real to virtual environments. Malware is unnecessary software that is often utilized to launch cyberattacks. Malware variants are still evolving by using advanced packing and obfuscation methods. These approaches make malware classification and detection more challenging. New techniques that are different from conventional systems should be utilized for effectively combating new malware variants. Machine learning (ML) methods are ineffective in identifying all complex and new malware variants. The deep learning (DL) method can be a promising solution to detect all malware variants. This paper presents an Automated Android Malware Detection using Optimal Ensemble Learning Approach for Cybersecurity.

(AAMD-OELAC) technique. The major aim of the AAMD-OELAC technique lies

in the automated classification and identification of Android malware. To achieve this, the AAMD-OELAC technique performs data preprocessing at the preliminary stage. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models, namely Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM), kernel extreme learning machine (KELM), and Regularized random vector functional link neural network (RRVFLN). Finally, the hunter-prey optimization (HPO) approach is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models, and it helps accomplish improved malware detection results. To denote the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC method, a comprehensive experimental analysis is conducted. The simulation results portrayed the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC technique over other existing approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Cybersecurity is becoming a main area of immediate concern to network engineers and computer scientists, so satisfying The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Binit Lukose . solutions to several problems are in order [1]. Consequently, the fast technological developments and their inherent integrations in every aspect of lifestyles, various malware apps, and targets become well-identified and studied [2]. Android malware is the malware variety that gained significant interest in the web world. One common operating system is Android, which dominates the operating system market [3]. Malware invasive methods emerge for avoiding identification, as few malware applications have more than 50 parameters that make detection a difficult one [4]. Hence, it is essential to devise techniques that deal with the continuous growth of Android malware to find it, deactivate or remove it efficiently. All these difficulties engage scholars in the area and urge them to continue more research to find malware and manage it properly [5].

Thus, researchers have developed three mechanisms to find Android malware such as dynamic, static, and hybrid analysis methods. Static analysis extracts the

features that assist in identifying harmful performance for apps without a demanding actual application deployment [6]. But this kind of analysis suffered from code obfuscation methods which assist help malware author to avoid static methods. Dynamic analysis can be used for determining the malware of apps in their runtime [7]. Commonly, the static analysis feature offers the capability of locating the malware element using source code, while the dynamic analysis feature offers the capability of finding the location of malware in a runtime environment. Android developers and users can be exposed to unnecessary risks and dangers with malware [8]. This study covers malware detection methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adversarial superiority in android malware detection: Lessons from reinforcement learning based evasion attacks and defenses

Today, android smartphones are being used by billions of users and thus have become a lucrative target of malware designers. Therefore being one step ahead in this zero-sum game of malware detection between the anti-malware community and malware developers is more of a necessity than

a desire. This work focuses on a proactive adversary-aware framework to develop adversarially superior android malware detection models. We first investigate the adversarial robustness of thirty-six distinct malware detection models constructed using two static features (permission and intent) and eighteen classification algorithms. We designed two Targeted Type-II Evasion Attacks (TRPO-MalEAttack and PPO-MalEAttack) based on reinforcement learning to exploit vulnerabilities in the above malware detection models.

The attacks aim to add minimum perturbations in each malware application and convert it into an adversarial application that can fool the malware detection models. The TRPO-MalEAttack achieves an average fooling rate of 95.75% (with 2.02 mean perturbations), reducing the average accuracy from 86.01% to 49.11% in thirty-six malware detection models. On the other hand, The PPO-MalEAttack achieves a higher average fooling rate of 96.87% (with 2.08 mean perturbations), reducing the average accuracy from 86.01% to 48.65% in the same thirty-six detection models. We also develop a list of the TEN most vulnerable android permissions and intents that

an adversary can use to generate more adversarial applications. Later, we propose a defense strategy (MalVPatch) to counter the adversarial attacks on malware detection models.

Android Malware Detection Based on a Hybrid Deep Learning Model

In recent years, the number of malware on the Android platform has been increasing, and with the widespread use of code obfuscation technology, the accuracy of antivirus software and traditional detection algorithms is low. Current state-of-the-art research shows that researchers started applying deep learning methods for malware detection. We proposed an Android malware detection algorithm based on a hybrid deep learning model which combines deep belief network (DBN) and gate recurrent unit (GRU). First of all, analyze the Android malware; in addition to extracting static features, dynamic behavioral features with strong antiobfuscation ability are also extracted. Then, build a hybrid deep learning model for Android malware detection. Because the static features are relatively independent, the DBN is used to process the static features. Because the dynamic features have temporal correlation, the GRU is used to process the dynamic feature

sequence. Finally, the training results of DBN and GRU are input into the BP neural network, and the final classification results are output. Experimental results show that, compared with the traditional machine learning algorithms, the Android malware detection model based on hybrid deep learning algorithms has a higher detection accuracy, and it also has a better detection effect on obfuscated malware.

Metaheuristics with Deep Learning Model for Cybersecurity and Android Malware Detection and Classification

Since the development of information systems during the last decade, cybersecurity has become a critical concern for many groups, organizations, and institutions. Malware applications are among the commonly used tools and tactics for perpetrating a cyberattack on Android devices, and it is becoming a challenging task to develop novel ways of identifying them. There are various malware detection models available to strengthen the Android operating system against such attacks. These malware detectors categorize the target applications based on the patterns that exist in the features present in the Android applications. As the analytics data continue to grow, they negatively affect the Android

defense mechanisms. Since large numbers of unwanted features create a performance bottleneck for the detection mechanism, feature selection techniques are found to be beneficial. This work presents a Rock Hyrax Swarm Optimization with deep learning-based Android malware detection (RHSODL-AMD) model.

On Deceiving Malware Classification with Section Injection

We investigate how to modify executable files to deceive malware classification systems. This work's main contribution is a methodology to inject bytes across a malware file randomly and use it both as an attack to decrease classification accuracy but also as a defensive method, augmenting the data available for training. It respects the operating system file format to make sure the malware will still execute after our injection and will not change its behavior. We reproduced five state-of-the-art malware classification approaches to evaluate our injection scheme: one based on Global Image Descriptor (GIST) + K-Nearest-Neighbors (KNN), three Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) variations and one Gated CNN. We performed our experiments on a public dataset with 9339 malware samples from

25 different families. Our results show that a mere increase of 7% in the malware size causes an accuracy drop between 25% and 40% for malware family classification. They show that an automatic malware classification system may not be as trustworthy as initially reported in the literature. We also evaluate using modified malware alongside the original ones to increase networks robustness against the mentioned attacks. The results show that a combination of reordering malware sections and injecting random data can improve the overall performance of the classification. All the code is publicly available.

Any software that does something that causes harm to a user, computer, or network can be considered malware [...]

EXISTING SYSTEM

Shaukat et al. [11] devise a new DL-related method for detecting malware. It delivered superior outcomes to classical methods by merging dynamic and static analysis benefits. Firstly, it visualizes a portable executable (PE) file as coloured images. Secondly, it extracted deep features from colour images utilizing fine-tuned DL method. Thirdly, it finds malware related to the deep features of SVM. Geremias et al. [12] presented a method using image-based DL called novel multi-view Android

malware identification, applied threefold. Firstly, as per the many feature sets in multi-view settings, apps were assessed, thereby raising the data presented for the classification. Secondly, the derived feature set is transformed into image formats while preserving the essential elements of data distribution, keeping the data for the classifier task. Thirdly, built images are collectively depicted in one shot, all in a predefined image channel, allowing the implementation of DL structure.

Kim et al. [13] modelled a malware detection system called MAPAS that attains higher precision and adaptable use of computational resources. MAPAS examined the performances of malicious apps based on API call graphs of them through CNN. However, the presented MAPAS technique does not utilize a classifier method produced by CNN, it uses CNN to find typical attributes of the API call graph of malware. Fallah and Bidgoly [14] developed a technique related to LSTM for detecting malware-having the capability of differentiating benign and malware samples and identifying and detecting unseen and new types of malware. In this study, the author has executed many studies to show the abilities of the presented technique, including new malware family detection, malware identification, malware family identification, as well as assessing the minimal time needed to find

malware.

Sihag et al. [15] introduced DL-based Android malware identification with the use of DYnamic features (De-LADY), a resilient obfuscation method. It has used behavioural features from dynamic analysis of an application performed in the emulated setting. Wang et al. [16] present a hybrid method related to DAE and CNN. Firstly, to enhance the precision of malware detection, the author reconstructed the high-dimensional feature of apps and used many CNN to find Android malware. Secondly, to diminish the training period, the author used DAE as a pre-training approach for CNN. With the consolidation, DAE and CNN method (DAE-CNN) can study flexible patterns quickly.

Yadav et al. [17] presented a performance comparison of 26 existing pretrained CNN methods in Android malware detection. Depending on the outcomes, to find Android malware, an EfficientNet-B4 CNN-based approach was devised with the use of an image-based malware representation of the Android DEX file. From the malware images, EfficientNet-B4 extracted relevant attributes. Masum and Shahriar [18] devised a DL structure named Droid-NNet, for classifying malware. But this technique Droid-NNet, is a deep learner that surpasses existing cutting-edge ML approaches. Idrees et al. [19] examine PIndroid – a new Permission and Intents-

based structure to detect Android malware applications. As we know, PIndroid is the primary solution, which utilizes a group of permissions and purposes supplemented with Ensemble approaches for correct malware detection. In [20], the authors establish that once the concept drift was discussed, permissions create long-lasting and effectual malware detection methods. Taha and Barukab [21] introduce a mechanism for Android malware classification utilizing optimizer ensemble learning depending on GA. The GA was utilized for optimizing the parameter settings from the RF technique for obtaining the maximum Android malware classifier accuracy. Sabanci et al. [22] intended to categorize pepper seeds belonging to distinct cultivars with CNN techniques. Two methods are presented for classification. Initially, the CNN approaches (ResNet50 and ResNet18) are trained for pepper seeds. Secondary, diverse in the first, the features of pre-training CNN approaches are fused, and feature selection has been executed to the fused features. In [23], the authors examine recent algorithms utilized for Android Malware Detection. As a result, an outline of the Android system exposed the underlying processes and the problems facing its security structure.

Disadvantages

- The complexity of data: Most of the existing machine learning models must be able to accurately interpret large and complex datasets to detect Android Malware Detection.
- Data availability: Most machine learning models require large amounts of data to create accurate predictions. If data is unavailable in sufficient quantities, then model accuracy may suffer.
- Incorrect labeling: The existing machine learning models are only as accurate as the data trained using the input dataset. If the data has been incorrectly labeled, the model cannot make accurate predictions

Proposed System

This paper presents an Automated Android Malware Detection using Optimal Ensemble Learning Approach for Cybersecurity (AAMD-OELAC) technique. The AAMDOELAC technique performs data preprocessing at the preliminary stage. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models, namely Least Square Support Vector Machine (LS-SVM), kernel extreme learning machine (KELM), and Regularized random vector functional link neural network (RRVFLN). Finally, the hunter-prey optimization (HPO) algorithm is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL

models, and it helps accomplish improved malware detection results. To indicate the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC approach, a comprehensive experimental analysis is carried out.

Advantages

- An intelligent AAMD-OELAC technique comprising data preprocessing, ensemble learning, and HPO-based hyperparameter tuning is presented for Android malware detection. To the best of our knowledge, the AAMD-OELAC technique never existed in the literature.
- Perform ensemble learning-based classification process comprising LS-SVM, KELM, and RRVFLN models for Android malware detection.
- The combination of the HPO algorithm and ensemble learning process improves the detection accuracy of Android malware. By utilizing multiple classifiers and optimization strategies, the model can effectively identify malicious patterns and behaviours in Android applications

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as

Train and Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Predicted Android Malware Detection Details, Find Predicted Android Malware Detection Ratio, Download Predicted Datasets, View Android Malware Predicted Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some

operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN, PREDICT ANDROID MALWARE TYPE, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

Decision tree classifiers

Decision tree classifiers are used successfully in many diverse areas. Their most important feature is the capability of capturing descriptive decision making knowledge from the supplied data. Decision tree can be generated from training sets. The procedure for such generation based on the set of objects (S), each belonging to one of the classes C1, C2, ..., Ck is as follows:

Step 1. If all the objects in S belong to the same class, for example Ci, the decision tree for S consists of a leaf labeled with this class

Step 2. Otherwise, let T be some test with possible outcomes O1, O2, ..., On. Each object in S has one outcome for T so the test partitions S into subsets S1, S2, ... Sn where each object in Si has outcome Oi for T. T becomes the root of the

decision tree and for each outcome O_i we build a subsidiary decision tree by invoking the same procedure recursively on the set S_i .

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

- **Simple, but a very powerful classification algorithm**
- **Classifies based on a similarity measure**
- **Non-parametric**
- **Lazy learning**
- **Does not “learn” until the test example is given**
- **Whenever we have a new data to classify, we find its K-nearest neighbors from the training data**

Example

- **Training dataset consists of k-closest examples in feature space**
- **Feature space means, space with categorization variables (non-metric variables)**
- **Learning based on instances, and thus also works lazily because instance close to the**

input vector for test or prediction may take time to occur in the training dataset

Logistic regression Classifiers

Logistic regression analysis studies the association between a categorical dependent variable and a set of independent (explanatory) variables. The name *logistic regression* is used when the dependent variable has only two values, such as 0 and 1 or Yes and No. The name *multinomial logistic regression* is usually reserved for the case when the dependent variable has three or more unique values, such as Married, Single, Divorced, or Widowed. Although the type of data used for the dependent variable is different from that of multiple regression, the practical use of the procedure is similar.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we have developed the design of the AAMD-OELAC technique for an accurate and automated Android malware detection process. The intention of the

AAMD-OELAC approach focused on the automatic recognition and classification of Android malware. To achieve this, the AAMD-OELAC technique encompasses data preprocessing, ensemble classification, and HPO-based parameter tuning. For the Android malware detection process, the AAMD-OELAC technique follows an ensemble learning process using three ML models namely LS-SVM, KELM, and RRVFLN. Finally, the HPO algorithm is exploited for the optimal parameter tuning of the three DL models and it helps in accomplishing improved malware detection results. To portray the supremacy of the AAMD-OELAC method, a wide-ranging experimental analysis is conducted. The simulation results portrayed the supremacy of the AAMDOELAC technique over other existing approaches. Future work could focus on developing more advanced techniques to capture and analyze fine-grained behaviours, enabling better detection of sophisticated malware. In addition, future work could explore privacy-preserving approaches such as secure multi-party computation or federated learning, which enable collaborative malware detection without compromising user privacy.

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